

Bridging the Healthcare Gap: Assessing Health Insurance Challenges and Solutions in Koshi Province, Nepal

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Abstract

Access to primary healthcare is a fundamental human right, but many low-and-middle-income countries, including Nepal, struggle with healthcare financing challenges that impede equitable access to essential services, despite attempts to lower out-of-pocket spending and increase enrollment in health insurance programs. This study assessed the health insurance program and its challenges for social security in Koshi Province, Nepal. Utilizing a descriptive cross-sectional design, the study surveyed 433 patients from outpatient departments in Koshi Province through structured interviews to explore demographics, health insurance enrollment, utilization, and challenges faced. Data analysis, performed using SPSS version 20. Findings show a predominantly Brahmin/Chhetri, Hindu, middle-class population, mainly aged 30-40, with a slight female majority, mostly married, and living in joint families, but reveal a caste-based skew, indicating the need for targeted outreach. While a majority of respondents are aware of health insurance, gaps in specific knowledge about service availability remain. High utilization of services is reported, yet barriers such as financial constraints and access issues persist. Participants express a strong need for continuous health insurance programs, and proposed solutions include enhancing awareness, reducing wait times, and expanding health facility networks. These insights underscore the necessity for improved social protection mechanisms and more effective implementation of health insurance programs to achieve equitable healthcare access in Nepal.

Keywords: *Challenges, Healthcare gap, Health insurance, Koshi province, Solutions*

Introduction

Access to primary health care is a fundamental human right, as highlighted by the Alma Ata Declaration in 1978, which sought to reduce health inequities worldwide. However, in many low-and-middle-income countries (LMICs), inadequate financing continues to hinder access to essential health services (Dalaba et al., 2017). Nepal, as a South Asian country categorized under LMIC, has made strides in increasing the number of health facilities. Yet, despite improvements in infrastructure, the country's healthcare financing remains insufficient, leading to a high reliance on private out-of-pocket spending, which accounts for 55% of total health expenditure (UNICEF, 2020).

In response to these challenges, the Government of Nepal introduced the National Health Insurance Policy in 2013 to improve healthcare access for marginalized and economically disadvantaged populations (Mishra, Khanal, et al., 2015). While this policy aimed to reduce the financial burden on families by covering a range of health services, participation rates remain low, with only 11.92% of the population enrolled in the program (Health Insurance Board, 2076). The reliance on out-of-pocket payments continues to place significant strain on low-income families, often forcing them to choose between healthcare costs and other essential expenses (Sirag & Nor, 2021).

The dual burden of communicable and non-communicable diseases in Nepal further exacerbates these challenges, with many families facing financial hardships due to healthcare costs (Mishra, Neupane, et al., 2015). Despite the government's efforts to provide subsidized healthcare for severe illnesses and to implement health insurance programs, barriers such as low coverage, increasing dropout rates, and ineffective implementation persist (Ranabhat et al., 2020). These ongoing issues underscore the urgent need for improved social protection mechanisms and more effective scaling of health insurance programs to ensure equitable access to healthcare services for all citizens. Thus, this study aimed to assess the health insurance program and its challenges for social security in Koshi Province, Nepal.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design using a quantitative research approach, focusing on 433 patients visiting outpatient departments (OPD) in Koshi Province. Participants were selected through purposive sampling from three hospitals (Khandbari hospital, Dhankuta hospital and Itahari hospital) of Koshi province. Data collection involved face-to-face interviews using structured questionnaires that gathered demographic information, healthcare service costs, and details on health insurance enrollment, coverage, utilization, and challenges. The data, analyzed using SPSS version 20, included descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations to summarize participant characteristics. Ethical considerations were carefully addressed, including informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality, ensuring that participants' data were securely stored and used exclusively for research purposes.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Respondent's Profile

Socio-demographic Characteristics		Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Geography	Mountain region	154	35.6%
	Hilly region	148	34.2%
	Terai region	131	30.3%
Age (years completed)	Less than 20 years	8	1.8%
	20-30 years	78	18.0%

	30-40 years	101	23.3%
	40-50 years	82	18.9%
	50-60 years	77	17.8%
	60 and above	87	20.1%
Gender	Male	196	45.3%
	Female	236	54.5%
	Others	1	0.2%
Caste	Brahmin/ Chhetri	237	54.7%
	Adibashi/Janajati	161	37.2%
	Madhesi	6	1.4%
	Dalit	25	5.8%
	Others	4	0.9%
Religion	Hinduism	371	85.7%
	Buddhism	38	8.8%
	Christianity	4	0.9%
	Kirat	17	3.9%
	Others	3	0.7%
Educational Status	Illiterate	29	6.7%
	No formal education	77	17.8%
	Basic Level (up to Class 8)	80	18.5%
	Secondary level (from 9-12)	178	41.1%
	Bachelor	56	12.9%
	Master Degree and above	13	3.0%
Occupation	Unemployed	70	16.2%
	Private employee	43	9.9%
	Government employee	31	7.2%
	Self-employed/ Entrepreneur	63	14.5%
	Foreign employment	6	1.4%
	Homemaker	194	44.8%
	Retried	18	4.2%
	Student	8	1.8%
Marital status	Married	388	89.6%
	Unmarried	36	8.3%
	Widow/Widower	8	1.8%
	Separated	1	0.2%
Family type	Nuclear	145	33.5%
	Joint	288	66.5%
Total no. of family members	Less than 5 members	131	30.3%
	5 and more members	302	69.7%
Presence of under five children	NO	292	67.4%
	Yes	141	32.6%
Presence of elderly (≥ 60 years of age) in the family	NO	200	46.2%
	Yes	233	53.8%
Presence of chronic illness	NO	208	48.0%

	Yes	225	52.0%
Average annual family income (NPR)	Less than 1lakh	103	23.8%
	1-5 lakhs	298	68.8%
	More than 5 lakhs	32	7.4%

Table 1 presents the socio-demographic features of study population which consists of diverse socio-demographic characteristics, with participants primarily from the mountain (35.6%) and hilly (34.2%) regions. The majority identify as Brahmin/Chhetri (54.7%) and Hindu (85.7%). Age distribution reveals a concentration in the 30-40 years range (23.3%), with a slight female majority (54.5%) and a high proportion of married individuals (89.6%). In terms of education, many have completed secondary schooling (41.1%), and a significant number are homemakers (44.8%). Families are predominantly joint (66.5%) with more than five members (69.7%). Most participants fall into the middle-class category (78.3%) and report an annual income of 1 to 5 lakhs NPR (68.8%). The presence of chronic illnesses and elderly family members highlights health-related challenges within this population.

Table 2: Factors Associated with Enrollment of Health Insurance in Koshi Province

Enrollment related factors		Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
General concept of health insurance	No	24	5.5%
	Yes	409	94.5%
Aspect of Health Insurance	Knowing about premium amount	367	84.8%
	Benefit ceiling	370	85.5%
	Time of renewal	334	77.1%
	Service availability	256	59.1%
	General Awareness	28	6.5%
Source of Information	From Insurance Agents	217	50.1%
	From Health Workers	281	64.9%
	From Friend/Relative/Neighbor	167	38.6%
	From Radio	19	4.4%
	From Newspapers	17	3.9%
	From Television	45	10.4%
	From Social Media	61	14.1%
Reasons for Enrollment in Health Insurance Program	Affordability of premiums	222	51.3%
	Coverage offered by the insurance plan	365	84.3%
	Previous experience with health issues	138	31.9%
Method of health insurance membership fee payment	From saving/salary	391	90.3%
	From loan	29	6.7%
	Others	13	3.0%
Family members currently enrolled in health insurance	Up to 5 members	311	71.8%
	More than 5 members	122	28.2%

Duration of health insurance membership	Less than 1 years	44	10.2%
	1-2 years	81	18.7%
	2-3 years	108	24.9%
	3 years and above	200	46.2%

This table 2 provides insights into enrollment-related factors for a health insurance program, presenting that most respondents (94.5%) have a general understanding of health insurance, with 84.8% aware of the premium amount and 85.5% knowledgeable about the benefit ceiling. Health workers (64.9%) and insurance agents (50.1%) are the main sources of information. Affordability and coverage are the primary reasons for joining the program, and 90.3% pay their membership fees through savings or salary. Most families (71.8%) enroll up to five members, with nearly half (46.2%) having been members for over three years.

Table 3: Utilization and coverage related factors of Health insurance

Utilization related variables		Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Utilization of Social Health Insurance (SHI) card for service benefits	No	9	2.1%
	Yes	424	97.9%
Experienced financial hardship before utilizing health insurance	No	167	38.6%
	Yes	266	61.4%
Importance of affordable health insurance premium in enrollment	Very Important	203	46.9%
	Important	203	46.9%
	Neutral	12	2.8%
	Less Important	6	1.4%
	Not Important	9	2.1%
First contacted point for health facility	Public	416	96.1%
	Private	17	3.9%
Time to reach health facility (first contact point) for SHI services	< 30 minutes	123	28.4%
	> 30 minutes	310	71.6%
Type of Morbidity	Minor morbidity	407	94.0%
	Major morbidity	26	6.0%
	Both	45	10.4%
Type of Social Health Security Scheme Utilized	Drugs	394	91.0%
	Out-patient service	364	84.1%
	Lab diagnostic services	386	89.1%
	In-patient services	67	15.5%
	Emergency services	106	24.5%
	Not utilized yet	7	1.6%
Frequency of Health Insurance Utilization	Regularly	332	76.7%
	Occasionally	94	21.7%
	Rarely	7	1.6%
Waiting Time for Social Health Security Services	<30 minutes	8	1.8%
	30-60 minutes	73	16.9%

	> 60 minutes	352	81.3%
Number of Times Family Member Used Social Health Security	1 time	22	5.1%
	2 times	50	11.5%
	3 times	75	17.3%
	4 times and more	286	66.1%
Sufficiency of Service Availability under SHI	Sufficient	249	57.5%
	Not sufficient	184	42.5%
Faced Difficulty Finding Healthcare Providers/Facilities that accept health insurance coverage	No	210	48.5%
	Yes	223	51.5%
Coverage related		Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Perception on Health Insurance Program	Reduced Out Of Pocket Expenditure	215	49.7%
	Improved Health Status	207	47.8%
	It should be continuously	392	90.5%
Family Members Diagnosed with Health Problems in the Past 12 Months	No	223	51.5%
	Yes	210	48.5%
Willingness to Continue Health Insurance Services	No	4	0.9%
	Yes	419	96.8%
	May be	10	2.3%

Table 3 presents variables related to the utilization of Social Health Insurance (SHI) services. Nearly all respondents (97.9%) have used their SHI card, with 61.4% experiencing financial hardship before enrolling. Affordable premiums are a critical factor for 93.8% of participants. Most people first contact public health facilities (96.1%) and take more than 30 minutes to reach them (71.6%). Minor ailments are the most common (94%), with drugs (91%) and lab diagnostics (89.1%) being the most utilized services. About 76.7% regularly use SHI, but 81.3% face long wait times. While 57.5% find SHI services sufficient, 51.5% report difficulty finding providers that accept insurance.

In terms of coverage perception, nearly half of the respondents (49.7%) believe that health insurance reduces out-of-pocket expenses, while 47.8% feel it has improved their health status. A substantial 90.5% express the need for continuous health insurance programs. While 51.5% of families reported having members diagnosed with health problems in the past year, an overwhelming majority (96.8%) are willing to continue utilizing health insurance services.

Table 4: Assessment of Healthcare Services and Facilities

S.N.	Service/Aspect	Frequency (%)	Worse (%)	Better (%)
1.	Availability of Medicines	73 (16.9)	21 (4.8)	339 (78.29)
2.	Quality of Medicines	84 (19.4)	29 (6.7)	320 (73.90)
3.	Availability of Laboratory Services	35 (8.1)	31 (7.2)	367 (84.8)
4.	Quality of Laboratory Service	43 (9.9)	41 (9.5)	349 (80.5)
5.	Waiting Time for Service	73 (16.9)	68 (15.7)	292 (67.4)

6.	Sanitation of Health Institutions	43 (9.9)	28 (6.5)	362 (83.6)
7.	Availability of Ambulance Service	59 (13.6)	24 (5.5)	350 (80.9)
8.	Availability of Referral Services	32 (7.4)	51 (11.8)	350 (80.9)
9.	Facilities (Toilets, Electricity, Water)	26 (6.0)	29 (6.7)	378 (87.2)
10.	Ease of Service	63 (14.5)	61 (14.1)	309 (71.4)
11.	Service Availability Time	39 (9.0)	75 (17.3)	319 (73.7)

Table 4 presents the assessment of healthcare services and facilities and represents patient perceptions across various areas. 73 respondents (16.9%) expressed concerns about the availability of medicines, while 339 participants (78.29%) noted improvements. Regarding quality, 84 participants (19.4%) reported issues with medicine quality, but 320 (73.90%) felt it had improved. Significant concerns were highlighted in waiting times, with 68 respondents (15.7%) experiencing worsening conditions, and sanitation issues reported by 28 participants (6.5%). Overall, while many aspects, such as laboratory services and ambulance availability, received positive feedback, critical areas like waiting times and service availability require attention to enhance patient satisfaction and service quality.

Table 5: Challenges of the health insurance program for social security in Koshi Province

Challenges		Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean	Std. Deviation
Unaware of renewal system	Strongly disagree	55	12.7%	2.88	1.073
	Disagree	88	20.3%		
	Neutral	172	39.7%		
	Agree	92	21.2%		
	Strongly agree	26	6.0%		
Long waiting time for health service	Strongly disagree	28	6.5%	3.51	1.052
	Disagree	47	10.9%		
	Neutral	89	20.6%		
	Agree	215	49.7%		
	Strongly agree	54	12.5%		
Limited health care services under SHI scheme	Strongly disagree	21	4.8%	3.55	1.144
	Disagree	77	17.8%		
	Neutral	68	15.7%		
	Agree	178	41.1%		
	Strongly agree	89	20.6%		
Unfriendly behavior of service provider	Strongly disagree	45	10.4%	2.66	.983
	Disagree	150	34.6%		
	Neutral	169	39.0%		
	Agree	46	10.6%		
	Strongly agree	23	5.3%		
Poor quality service	Strongly disagree	46	10.6%	2.69	.964
	Disagree	132	30.5%		
	Neutral	187	43.2%		
	Agree	48	11.1%		
	Strongly agree	20	4.6%		
Longer distance to	Strongly disagree	46	10.6%	3.21	1.368

health facility	Disagree	129	29.8%		
	Neutral	47	10.9%		
	Agree	110	25.4%		
	Strongly agree	101	23.3%		
Unable to pay insurance premium	Strongly disagree	20	4.6%	3.36	1.020
	Disagree	54	12.5%		
	Neutral	170	39.3%		
	Agree	128	29.6%		
	Strongly agree	61	14.1%		
Poor trust on Social health insurance	Strongly disagree	29	6.7%	2.82	.896
	Disagree	110	25.4%		
	Neutral	223	51.5%		
	Agree	50	11.5%		
	Strongly agree	21	4.8%		
Services not used as no one got sick during enrolment period	Strongly disagree	22	5.1%	3.50	1.078
	Disagree	44	10.2%		
	Neutral	148	34.2%		
	Agree	132	30.5%		
	Strongly agree	87	20.1%		

Table 5 outlines the perception of challenges reported by respondents regarding the health insurance program. Many (39.7%) were neutral about awareness of the renewal system, with only 12.7% strongly disagreeing about lack of awareness, resulting in a mean score of 2.88. Long waiting times were highlighted as a major issue, with 49.7% agreeing and a mean score of 3.51. Limited services under the Social Health Insurance (SHI) scheme were acknowledged by 41.1%, yielding a mean score of 3.55. Perceptions of unfriendly service provider behavior and distance to healthcare facilities contributed to dissatisfaction, with mean scores of 2.66 and 3.21, respectively. Financial concerns were prevalent, with 39.3% neutral about paying insurance premiums and a notable percentage reporting non-utilization of services due to lack of illness during enrollment. These findings indicate significant areas for improvement in healthcare access and delivery.

Table 6: Solutions to tackle the challenges of Social health security scheme

Solutions		Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. Improved awareness campaigns and renewal system	Not effective at all	7	1.6%	4.19	0.667
	Ineffective	4	0.9%		
	Neutral	9	2.1%		
	Effective	293	67.7%		
	Highly effective	120	27.7%		
2. Reduction of waiting times for health services	Not effective at all	4	0.9%	4.24	0.721
	Ineffective	5	1.2%		
	Neutral	34	7.9%		
	Effective	231	53.3%		
	Highly effective	159	36.7%		
3. Expansion of the network of health	Not effective at all	4	0.9%	4.42	0.663
	Ineffective	2	0.5%		

facilities	Neutral	12	2.8%		
	Effective	204	47.1%		
	Highly effective	211	48.7%		
4. Ensuring availability of services and drugs when needed	Not effective at all	3	0.7%	4.46	0.649
	Ineffective	3	0.7%		
	Neutral	10	2.3%		
	Effective	191	44.1%		
	Highly effective	226	52.2%		
5. Training programs for service providers on interpersonal skills	Not effective at all	3	0.7%	4.27	0.739
	Ineffective	11	2.5%		
	Neutral	24	5.5%		
	Effective	222	51.3%		
	Highly effective	173	40.0%		
6. Initiatives to improve overall service quality	Not effective at all	2	0.5%	4.41	0.647
	Ineffective	5	1.2%		
	Neutral	11	2.5%		
	Effective	210	48.5%		
	Highly effective	205	47.3%		
7. Expansion of the coverage and benefits of the SHI scheme	Not effective at all	1	0.2%	4.52	0.593
	Ineffective	4	0.9%		
	Neutral	4	0.9%		
	Effective	183	42.3%		
	Highly effective	241	55.7%		
8. Flexible payment plans and subsidies for insurance premiums	Not effective at all	2	0.5%	4.34	0.647
	Ineffective	2	0.5%		
	Neutral	24	5.5%		
	Effective	225	52.0%		
	Highly effective	180	41.6%		
9. Trust-building campaigns for the Social Health Insurance scheme	Not effective at all	2	0.5%	4.46	0.596
	Ineffective	2	0.5%		
	Neutral	5	1.2%		
	Effective	211	48.7%		
	Highly effective	213	49.2%		
10. Collaboration with private healthcare providers	Not effective at all	4	0.9%	4.57	0.660
	Ineffective	3	0.7%		
	Neutral	8	1.8%		
	Effective	144	33.3%		
	Highly effective	274	63.3%		
11. Promotional activities to encourage utilization of services	Not effective at all	3	0.7%	4.41	0.614
	Ineffective	2	0.5%		
	Neutral	5	1.2%		
	Effective	226	52.2%		
	Highly effective	197	45.5%		

Table 6 analyzes strategies to address challenges in the Social Health Insurance program in Koshi Province, based on participant feedback. Key solutions include improving awareness

campaigns (67.7% effective, 27.7% highly effective, mean 4.19), reducing waiting times (53.3% effective, 36.7% highly effective, mean 4.24), and expanding health facility networks (47.1% effective, 48.7% highly effective, mean 4.42). Ensuring availability of services and drugs (52.2% highly effective, mean 4.46), training service providers (40% highly effective, mean 4.27), and collaborating with private providers (63.3% highly effective, mean 4.57) were also well-received. The data indicates strong support for these solutions, especially those related to service expansion, quality, and affordability.

Discussion

The socio-demographic analysis of the respondents reveals a well-distributed geographical representation across Mountain, Hilly, and Terai regions, suggesting that the health insurance program reaches various areas effectively. The diversity in age groups, including both middle-aged and elderly individuals, underscores the program's broad appeal. However, the demographic profile shows a predominance of females and higher representation of Brahmin/Chhetri and Adibashi/Janajati caste groups, with lower participation from Dalits. This demographic skew suggests that the program may not fully address the diverse needs of all social groups, particularly marginalized populations. The need for targeted outreach and tailored interventions is further supported by the findings of Ghimire et al. (2019), which underscore the necessity of extending health insurance coverage to disadvantaged households to enhance equity and advance universal health coverage.

Regarding enrollment, the high level of general understanding of health insurance among respondents is promising, with 94.5% being aware of health insurance principles. However, awareness of specific elements such as service availability is comparatively lower, which highlights a gap in comprehensive information dissemination. This finding aligns with Rad et al. (2024), which emphasizes that access to essential services and socio-demographic factors significantly influence satisfaction levels among insured and uninsured individuals. Moreover, the significant role of health workers and insurance agents in disseminating information indicates the importance of strengthening these channels. Enrollment decisions are heavily influenced by factors such as coverage and affordability, and the sustained engagement of a substantial proportion of respondents suggests that the program is valued, especially for those with prior health issues. This is reflecting insights from previous studies, such as those by Debpuur et al. (2015) and Agyepong et al. (2016), where insured individuals often seek care for minor issues to maximize benefits. The fact that 46.2% of respondents have been enrolled for over three years suggests sustained engagement, facilitated by paying membership fees from savings or salary and enrolling multiple family members. Despite this, challenges like financial barriers and issues with accessibility persist, indicating areas where the program could enhance its support and service delivery, echoing the concerns raised by Khanal et al. (2023) regarding the limitations of the NHIP due to policy and implementation challenges.

Utilization patterns indicate that while engagement with SHI services is high, with 97.9% using their cards, a significant number of respondents encounter financial difficulties before accessing services, underscoring the program's role in mitigating healthcare costs. Accessibility issues are evident, as 71.6% take over 30 minutes to reach public health facilities, and difficulties in finding SHI-accepting providers further compound these challenges. These are corroborated by Paudel (2021), who noted that distance to healthcare facilities hampers enrollment rates, as enrollment

assistants struggle to engage remote populations. Despite high regular usage, long wait times and some dissatisfaction with service adequacy are notable concerns, paralleling the results of Rad et al. (2024) and Agyepong et al. (2016).

Mixed perceptions about service adequacy suggest that there are areas needing attention to ensure comprehensive and effective service delivery. Nearly half of the respondents believe the program effectively reduces out-of-pocket expenses and improves health outcomes, reflecting strong support for its continuation. However, skepticism undermines efforts to boost enrollment and limit dropout rates, as seen in studies by Kamuzora & Gilson (2007) and Dror et al. (2016). This skepticism is particularly pertinent in light of findings from Gyanwali (2022), which detail prevalent health issues among NHIP beneficiaries, indicating a critical need for enhanced service delivery in these domains.

The evaluation of healthcare services and facilities since the implementation of the health insurance program shows notable improvements in areas such as medicine availability, laboratory services, and basic amenities. However, there were mixed perceptions about the overall ease of accessing services, with a notable proportion of respondents reporting both improvements and declines. This distrust aligns with findings from Paudel (2021) and the study by Khanal et al. (2023). This indicates that while the health insurance program has significantly advanced healthcare services and infrastructure, addressing remaining challenges in service accessibility and efficiency remains important for further progress.

To address these challenges, respondents suggested various solutions, with high support for enhancing awareness campaigns, streamlining the renewal system, reducing waiting times, and expanding the network of health facilities. This need for improved awareness is also emphasized by Panday (2019), who noted that limited awareness remains a barrier to enrolling the entire target population. Additionally, improving the availability of services, training providers, and building trust through flexible payment plans and private sector involvement were identified as effective strategies. These suggestions are in line with Rad et al. (2024), who found that overall satisfaction with health services was lower among both insured and uninsured individuals in Ethiopia; however, insured patients reported higher satisfaction than their uninsured counterparts. This pattern mirrors findings from a prior study in Ghana by Debpuur et al. (2015), which highlighted that insured individuals often visit health facilities for even minor issues to fully utilize their benefits. Moreover, Paneru et al. (2022) discuss how social cohesion and solidarity within local communities are vital for promoting awareness of the benefits of Community-Based Health Insurance (CBHI) and, ultimately, for supporting social health insurance programs and other social security initiatives. This comprehensive approach highlights the need for multifaceted solutions to enhance service provision, quality, and participant satisfaction within the National Health Insurance Program.

Conclusion

The research on assessment of health insurance program and its challenges for social security in Koshi Province reveals that the NHIP demonstrates promising enrollment figures and a high level of awareness regarding health insurance principles, with affordability and coverage as the main motivating factors for enrollment, with most participants relying on public health facilities.

Despite high utilization rates of SHI services, issues such as long waiting times, difficulty finding providers accepting insurance, and financial hardships before enrollment persist. Perceptions of SHI were generally positive, with many believing it reduces out-of-pocket expenses and improves health status. However, areas for improvement remain, particularly regarding service availability and patient experiences with waiting times and facility conditions. Overall, the study underscores the necessity for ongoing enhancements to the health insurance framework to address identified challenges and ensure effective healthcare delivery in the region.

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